

Discussion paper on sustainability standards and competitiveness

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

MATS Deliverable 3.6

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www.sustainable-agri-trade.eu

1. Summary

The deliverable 3.6 aims at developing a discussion on the assessment of collected data and their implications with regard to competitiveness and sustainability standards relevant in the agricultural trade context. The information and data, collected and presented in the [deliverable D3.4](#)¹, has undergone an initial standardisation phase, for making it useful as input in several WP's within the MATS consortium (see Figure 2: [MATS analytical framework, D2.4](#), p. 21).

The aim of this discussion paper is to further define and clarify the perimeters of the concept of sustainability within international trade, with a focus on the issue of labour (as an indicator of social sustainability) and environmental impacts (CO₂ eq.). This discussion paper focuses on the dynamics created within two case studies: CS#10 and CS#13.

Throughout D3.4, detailed work was carried out on the collection of relevant data on environmental, economic and social sustainability.

Since these sustainability dimensions and corresponding data and measures are deeply interlinked, it is essential to process the three related sustainability dimensions and related governance issues here: labor laws at the same time in a synergetic approach: the coexistence of these makes it possible to better understand conditions for a more sustainable international trade system.

In order to process the data in a comprehensive manner and in line with the MATS analytical framework (D2.4), the construction of causal loop diagrams (CLDs) was chosen as methodological approach. CLDs can be described as graphs that schematically represent the different variables and existing links, highlighting the likely consequences that the variation of one value has on the entire system.

The cause-effect system is emphasised graphically, yet it is also possible to extend this graphical reading by integrating a mathematical algorithm to this

¹ Link to the deliverables: <https://zenodo.org/records/7885586#.ZF DYCM5BxD8>

system of connections, which allows the values and variables collected from the previous D3.4 to be interconnected.

By introducing a sequence of mathematical relationships, it is possible to modify the values of specific items and visualise the variations. In this way, it is possible to build a sector-specific model, as was done within MATS for the dairy and beef sectors. The next step allows this dynamic representation to be adapted and customised for each individual partner country.

Data collected in the context of research in the economic, environmental and social areas were subjected to the standardisation process.

For **economic sustainability**, the data of interest are:

- farm size (no. of cattle per farm, no. of land used (ha), no. of labour units per farm);
- production and labour costs, expressed in €/100 kg CW -for beef- and €/100 kg of milk produced -for dairy;
- personnel costs (€/hour)
- prices (€/100 kg cw sold -for beef- and €/100 kg milk for dairy)
- subsidies (decoupled payments in €/100 kg of cw sold for beef or subsidies in €/100 kg milk produced)
- data on import and export (tons) and related tariffs (%);

With regard to the **social context**, information was collected on;

- working conditions (working time, education, paid leaves, occupational health and safety, social welfare, payments, trade right, child work)
- living wages.

And lastly, for the **environmental impact**, data were collected on the production of CO₂ eq., more specifically:

- kg CO₂eq./100 kg milk for dairy sector;
- kg CO₂-eq./kg of meat, or kg CO₂-eq./kg of carcass weight, or kg CO₂-eq./kg of free bone meat, or kg CO₂-eq./kg of protein.

The standardisation process is crucial since it allows the results of the different CLDs to be comparable. This is a fundamental step considering that

international trade requires an overall view of different countries and commodities (here dairy and beef) at the same time.

The application of the mathematical model also makes it possible to develop a series of scenarios, allowing different adaptation and mitigation strategies to be developed for the commodities (beef, dairy) and countries (Algeria, Germany, U.S.) considered. In addition, the scenarios allow the assessment of trade relations between the different countries.

This discussion paper helps to elucidate cross-effects among the different sustainability dimensions and implications (e.g. lower prices, but at what cost?), thereby also clarifying what it means to be more “competitive” (highlighting the importance of product and process quality, and the role of qualified personnel). Focusing on social and environmental sustainability in relation to international trade of beef and dairy products, this discussion paper provides a discussion base for policymakers and other transition path stakeholders, which is deeply grounded in the SDGs and country-level labor conditions. The discussion paper assesses the weight of labour costs in production across countries and aims to help improve understanding of the role of local legislation in strengthening product competitiveness. In addition, it assesses how governance (labor laws) may impact the farm competitiveness and trade of beef and dairy commodities. With the help of CLDs, different trade dynamics scenarios are explored for beef and dairy, especially with regard to expected impacts in Algeria, Germany and the U.S. The scenarios for these countries were to reach self-sufficiency. This implies that production in Algeria increased, and in Germany and the US declined. In the case of Algeria, we also increased salaries to improve social sustainability. These scenarios not only identify expected changes in the trade dynamics between countries, yet also highlight the potential for higher national sectoral profitability in Algeria, as well as the potential of a national CO₂eq. reduction in the case of Germany and the US. Overall, the discussion paper suggests that when competitiveness is considered as a key criterion for economic sustainability, important trade-offs arise among economic, social and environmental sustainability implications once the national diversity of governance and social conditions (labor laws and labor conditions) is taken into account.

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3. Introduction

Working conditions and environmental impact have a highly significant implication on each country's market positioning on the competitiveness of the product on international trade. The factors mentioned here have a wide variability that depends on the geographic location, legislation and local rules.

The economic aspect adds complexity to the socio-environmental scenario, and the values collected provide a key context in then developing the different scenarios that will be described at the end of the paper.

MATS is a project that has sustainability as its goal and therefore must necessarily be aligned with the SDGs that set out, in the context of the 2030 Agenda, the target baselines and direction to follow. The analysis carried out in the context of this assessment clearly coincides with some of these SDGs, including:

- **SDG 1: No Poverty**
Labour legislation contribute to reduce poverty and improve the livelihoods of workers and their families.
- **SDG 2: Zero Hunger**
Labour legislation support the promotion of sustainable livestock and agricultural practices, ensuring food safety and quality standards and addressing issues such as child labour and forced labour.
- **SDG 3: Good health and safety**
Having good legislation means being able to guarantee fair working practices and ensure the welfare of workers. Some aspects that need to be ensured are safety in the workplace, heavy and dangerous work, that could have a significant impact on personal integrity.
- **SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth**
Labor legislation aligns with SDG 8, which aims to promote inclusive and sustainable economic growth, productive employment, and decent work for all. Adequate labour laws can protect workers' rights, ensure fair wages, provide safe working conditions, and promote equal opportunities.

In addition to these main goals, there are links to some other objectives related to environmental and economic sustainability.

- **SDG 6:** *Clean water and sanitation*
- **SDG 13:** *Climate action*
- **SDG 15:** *Life on land*

The assessment of sustainability will therefore be based on indicators (and disclosures, in the case of social equity), implementing this system within the CLD.

The choice of the SDGs was a logical step from the perspective of a project contextualised at a time of high ambitions for sustainability from a global perspective (the establishment of SDGs in 2015). However, it emerged that a more in-depth analysis could be carried out by unpacking SDG 8, which is the main goal chosen to describe the social sphere through working conditions, into more point-specific and practice-oriented disclosures. This method, borrowed from earlier work "*Addressing the SDG goals through substantiation with the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) indicators*" (Langeneck L., Steiner B., 2022)", allows us to assess sustainability by individual issues, which then, when compared, offer a way of evaluating sustainability in this area and contextualise it in the economic and environmental framework.

Relating synthetic data on social and environmental sustainability with competitiveness data expressed in indicators allows the construction and comparison through reflections and connections facilitated by the CLD graphical representation, which in turn is enriched by the introduction of the mathematical model.

4. Available data and methodology

The data used for the analysis of environmental and socio-economic sustainability were collected in the previous work, D3.4. The methodology applied to conduct the sustainability analysis of the beef and dairy trade has been developed on three different levels, depending on whether it concerns the *economic, social, or environmental component*.

In terms of the **economic dimension**, the data collected using the typical farm method, provide detailed insights into the farm structures in different countries. These data have been processed to create tables to facilitate cross-sectional analysis. These quantitative data contain essential information such as labour costs and average incomes, which are closely linked to the social component. Indicator data for the different typical farms were collected by specific organisations including Agri-benchmark⁴ for beef and IFCN⁵ for dairy. In order to better define import/export relations, rankings were created for each partner country, highlighting the top five countries with which the main trade exchanges take place. By referring to existing databases, the tariffs were also brought up to date.

The methodology for the **environmental component** analysis was different for the two case studies. For milk, a database is available from IFCN and the impact has been investigated using emissions in terms of kg CO₂/100 kg milk produced. For the case study on beef, a bibliographic search of the available literature was carried out as there is currently no single global dataset. In addition, for both case studies the emissions connected to the transportation of products have been estimated, according to volumes (in tonnes), average distances (focusing on major trade centres) and using coefficients provided by the IPCC.

The **social impact analysis** was based on the research of working conditions in the case study countries, based on a challenging investigation of the national contracts and/or labour laws in each single country involved in the

⁴ <http://www.agribenchmark.org/beef-and-sheep.html>

⁵ <https://ifcndairy.org/>

two case studies. Each national contract or law has been examined in order to identify indicators that are common in all of them (e.g. working time per day, trainings, parental leaves, pay in case of illness, retirement, holidays, payments, etc, with the aim of constructing a database with consistent information for each country.

The result is a database, divided into several parts, as following:

- general information;
- working time;
- education;
- paid leaves;
- occupational health and safety;
- social welfare;
- payments;
- trade right;
- other regulation;
- child work.

Each of these parts is divided into a multitude of sections (more than fifty) that provide detailed information.

In this way, a first raw database has been created. Then, as indicators are not always expressed in the same way in the different national contracts, this first version has been processed and information related to each indicator of each country has been “translated” and standardised, in order to allow quick geographical comparisons. An example of this process can be represented through *working time*: to obtain the number of hours per day and per week, some “equivalences” have been performed (some countries for example expressed it as day/month), with the aim to be able to display in the database consistent and comparable values. Each indicator has undergone this process.

This qualitative data corresponds to the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) that have been selected for the case study and they are aligned with practical aspects through their conversion into GRI⁶ (Global Reporting Initiative) disclosure. This approach allows us to first investigate the efforts

⁶ "Addressing the SDG goals through substantiation with the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) indicators" (Langeneck L., Steiner B., 2022)

made by each country to promote development-oriented policies that support productive activities, decent job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation and encourage the formalization and growth of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises. It is crucial to protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, including migrant workers, in particular women migrants and those in precarious employment.

This study enables to analyse similarities and differences that can make the understanding of cross-effects clearer (e.g. lower prices, but at what cost?) or more 'competitive' (importance of product and process quality, qualified personnel).

However, it is to be noted that although the analysis has attempted to achieve a high degree of detail, it is not possible to fully represent a world made up of exceptions, special cases and realities that can differ from what is desired and no sufficient data are available to cover grey areas (e.g. no child labour, undeclared work).

5. Quick overview of case studies of interest

The analysis of environmental and social sustainability is applied to two different case studies, number #10 and #13. In the following, a quick overview of the structure of the case studies and the countries involved will be given.

The aim of these two case studies is to highlight key aspects that can be addressed to make international trade of beef and dairy products more sustainable, particularly when considering geographically distant countries. Another objective is to assess the weight of labour costs in production across different partner countries and to understand the role of local legislation in strengthening product competitiveness. In addition, it will be explored how working conditions and costs impact the farm competitiveness and trade of beef and dairy commodities.

5.1 Case study 10: Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development

Case study no. 10, *"Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development"*, aims to investigate the impact that labour conditions and costs have on the competitiveness of the product on international trade. Nine countries are involved in this case study: Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany, Italy, United States of America, South Africa, Morocco, Namibia.

FIGURE 1 COUNTRIES PARTICIPATING IN #CS10

Source: CRPA elaboration

In Europe, the land use in beef farms is relatively small: the higher value is in German typical farm (4,700 head sold/year, 175 ha of land availability), while it is significantly higher in Africa and South America where the bigger typical farms have 2,000 hectares of land available. In Europe, land availability is limited and there are [regulations](#) concerning the prohibition of deforestation and the import/export of meat from farms that have carried out these practices⁷.

Production costs are calculated in each typical farm and expressed in €/100 kg of Carcass Weight (CW) sold. The EU typical farms produce beef from a minimum cost of 465 €/100 kg CW in a medium German farm with 285 heads sold on average per year to a maximum cost of 699 €/100 kg CW in a French farm of 75 heads size.

The cost level is different in typical farms located in South America, where the total cost of production ranges from 239 €/100 kg of CW (in large Brazilian farms, up to 5,000 heads/year sold) to a maximum level of 628 €/100 kg CW (in small Brazilian farms of 35 heads/year sold). Argentinian farms are producing at an intermediate level in between those extreme values.

In Africa, the production can vary significantly depending on the area under analysis. In Morocco the cost of production ranges from a minimum of 620 €/100 kg CW (in larger farms of 280 heads) to 1,299 €/100 kg CW (in small farms with 2 heads). In Namibia, the cost of production ranges from a minimum of 264 €/100 kg of CW in large farms with 25,000 heads to a maximum of 349 €/100 kg of CW in a 600 heads farm. South African production costs are similar to Namibia.

Subsequently, the labour factor was examined, both in terms of the number of work units per farm and in terms of labour costs. In large typical farms in Namibia and South Africa the number of working units are between 35 and 45. In large farms in Argentina and USA the working units are in between 20 and 27. In other typical farms the most common is to have less than 10 working unites.

The total labour cost is a crucial point. It is possible to see that the cost is on average higher in Morocco (approx. 150 €/100 kg CW), where family labour plays a key role in beef production. Low labour cost is recorded in the United

⁷https://environment.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/COM_2021_706_1_EN_ACT_part1_v6.pdf

States, South Africa and Namibia, where, however, hired labour prevails (about 15 €/100 kg CW). In Germany and France there is a higher weight of family labour, while in Italy the average value is lower and hired labour is diffused.

A key factor to consider is the salary level. Average wages are higher in the European continent, particularly in Germany. Also United States of America shows good salary level. Values fall when investigating South American countries, particularly Brazil, and Africa where the wages are below 5 €/hour.

The wage per hour itself is not sufficient to describe the working conditions and the sustainability level in different countries. Local purchasing power can be very different from country to country, and consequently the standard living wage⁸ can differ substantially. The living wages of the investigated countries were extracted from the Living Wage Global Dataset (*Vionnet & Sacayon 2023*) indicating the cost of living in different categories including: food, housing and non-food and non-housing costs.

In Morocco a worker can live with an annual salary of 4,908 US dollars while in USA an individual needs 6.5 times the amount calculated for Morocco. For typical families the differences are much smaller.

TABLE 1 LIVING WAGE GLOBAL DATASET, CS #10

Country	LW for a Typical family (USD/year)	LW Standard family (USD/year)	LW Single individual (USD/year)	LW Single working parent family (USD/year)
Morocco	4.693	4.706	4.908	8.891
Argentina	5.565	5.996	5.894	10.643
Brazil	6.634	7.276	7.245	12.384
Namibia	8.961	9.743	10.802	15.304
South Africa	10.280	9.383	11.601	17.602
France	13.755	14.999	17.388	26.428
Germany	13.902	16.092	19.153	27.308
Italy	13.994	16.493	18.389	26.659
United States	22.714	25.560	32.121	44.212

Source: Living Wage Global Dataset - Vionnet & Sacayon 2023

The export flows of beef products were highlighted. Africa is a net importer and gets beef products from both Europe and America. America exports all

⁸ Living Wage Global Dataset (*Vionnet & Sacayon 2023*)

over the world. Italy, France and Germany have a strong trade relationship, facilitated by internal Union policies.

Finally, to draw a global overview of the “history” of **emissions** linked to agri-food system, reference has been done to the FAO report, “*Tackling climate change through livestock: A global assessment of emissions and mitigation opportunities*” (FAO, 2013) and to other FAO/FAOSTAT reports (FAO, 2016; FAO 2019; FAOSTAT 2000-2020). The patterns of GHG emissions (e.g. proportions among species/commodities as for the global impact) are quite consolidated and livestock sector plays an important role in climate change, with GHG emissions along livestock supply chains estimated at 7.1 gigatonnes CO₂-eq. per annum, representing 14.5% of all human-induced emissions.

Cattle (beef and milk) are the main contributor to the agri-food sector’s emissions with about 4.6 gigatonnes CO₂-eq., representing 65% of sector emissions (FAO, 2013). Comparing the two, beef and dairy generate similar amounts of GHG emissions, but beef slightly more. In fact, beef is the commodity with highest total emissions and emission intensities: it contributes 2.9 gigatonnes CO₂-eq. (41% of total sector emissions). When emissions are expressed on a per protein basis, beef is the commodity with the highest emission intensity (amount of GHGs emitted per unit of output produced), with an average of over 300 kg CO₂-eq. per kg of protein (FAO, 2013).

Comparing emissions of beef sector in the single countries taken into account in case study no. 10 has been quite challenging, due to the fact that this science is relatively new, not completely standardized and in constant evolution. This can lead to difference in unit of:

- measurement (kg CO₂-eq./kg of meat, or kg CO₂-eq./kg of carcass weight, or kg CO₂-eq./kg of free bone meat, or kg CO₂-eq./kg of protein),
- system boundary (segment of the production process that is considered)
- allocation (distribution of GHG emissions to different products occurring in multi-outputs productions).

Anyway, the order of size of data is very informative and can lead to interesting considerations.

In a nutshell, as for Europe, the emissions of the German beef sector vary from 13.6 kg CO₂-eq./kg of meat (Reinhardt G et al., 2020) to 26.9 kg CO₂-eq./kg of bone free meat (Mieleitner J at al., 2012); in France, from 17.4 kg CO₂-eq./kg of meat (Dollé J et al., 2012) to 40.0 kg CO₂-eq./kg of bone free

meat (Nguyen TTH et al., 2012), and in Italy from 15.3 kg CO₂-eq./kg of bone free meat (Benatti L et al., 2012) to 27.3 kg CO₂-eq./kg of bone free meat (Lesschen JP et al., 2011). So, Germany records the lowest and France the highest.

In the U.S., the emissions of beef sector vary from 22.30 to 41.73 CO₂eq./kg meat (Gerber PJ et al., 2013).

The beef sector of Latin America and Caribbean considered as a whole, according to Gerber PJ et al. (2013) produces from 49 to 69 CO₂-eq./kg meat. In Argentina, the emissions of beef sector vary from 22 (González AD et al., 2011) to 35 CO₂-eq./kg meat (Benatti L et al., 2015), while in Brazil from 9.2 (Dick, M et al., 2014) to 64 CO₂-eq./kg meat (Mieleitner J et al., 2012).

Considering it as a whole, according to Gerber PJ et al. (2013), Sub-Saharan Africa produces 100.72 CO₂-eq./kg meat, while North Africa produces 40 CO₂-eq./kg meat.

5.2 Case study 13: dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets

Case study no. 13, entitled "*Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets*", aims to investigate the impact that labour conditions and costs have on the competitiveness of the product on international trade. Nine countries are involved in this case study: Algeria, Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany, Italy, United States of America, South Africa, Zimbabwe.

According to the IFCN, among the project partner countries, the United States, Germany and South Africa host the biggest farms in their respective continents (no. cows per farm). Beyond farm size, it is important to emphasise the different production costs, which give an insight into the competitiveness of different holdings.

FIGURE 2 COUNTRIES PARTICIPATING IN #CS13

Source: CRPA elaboration

In Europe, production costs are highest in Germany (from 39 to 79.4 €/100 kg milk), while France and Italy are evenly balanced (approximately 40 €/100 kg milk). On the American continent, Argentina produces at the lowest cost (about 22 €/100 kg milk), as does South Africa (25 €/100 kg milk circa). For an understanding of actual efficiency, it is necessary to examine how much income actually covers expenses: only in South Africa, Argentina and in some Brazilian farms, incomes are able to cover production costs.

Labour cost can have a very different impact in terms of costs ranging from about 1.3 € to produce milk with 800 cows in South Africa up to 27.4 € to produce milk in a small 30 cows family farm in Germany. It is also clear that smaller farms in different countries are managed by family members (Germany, France, Algeria, USA, Brazil) on the contrary in larger typical farms the impact of the family labour is very limited and in some cases absent.

To give an additional insight on this economic element, it is important at this stage to also report the different *wage levels* (Living Wage Global Dataset-Vionnet & Sacayon 2023). It is emerging clearly the huge difference in terms of paid salary in different typical farm of the globe.

TABLE 2 LIVING WAGES, CS #13

Country	LW for a Typical family (USD/year)	LW Standard family (USD/year)	LW Single individual (USD/year)	LW Single working parent family (USD/year)
Algeria	4.813	4.382	4.080	9.062
Argentina	5.565	5.996	5.894	10.643
Brazil	6.634	7.276	7.245	12.384
South Africa	10.280	9.383	11.601	17.602
France	13.755	14.999	17.388	26.428
Germany	13.902	16.092	19.153	27.308
Italy	13.994	16.493	18.389	26.659
United States	22.714	25.560	32.121	44.212
Zimbabwe	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

Source: Living Wage Global Dataset - Vionnet & Sacayon 2023

In EU and USA countries the minimum salary level is about 12 €/hour and the maximum is up to 18 €/hour in some specific typical farms in France and USA. The salary level is ranging between 2 and 6 €/hour in the most competitive typical farms in South Africa, Argentina and Brazil. The salary level in Algeria and Zimbabwe is very low, ranging between 0.3-1.1 €/hour, yet needs to be converted. In particular, the wages per hour itself is not sufficient to describe the working conditions and the sustainability level in different countries. Local purchasing power can be very different from country to country, and consequently the standard living wage can differ a lot (Carr, 2023; Jarosz, 1996; van Ween et al., 2022).

Finally, the **export flows** of dairy products were highlighted. Europe exports all over the world, especially the connection between Italy-France-Germany is very strong, facilitated by internal Union policies. Africa is a net importer and gets dairy products from both Europe and America. More competitive countries with lower cost of production and self-sufficient in dairy production are in general exporting commodities in less competitive countries.

The recorded emissions available from the IFCN network, expressed in kg CO₂/100 kg milk SCM, shows that in Europe, Italy is the country with the highest average emissions (about 142 kg CO₂-eq/100 kg milk).

In Africa, the highest average emission is recorded in Algeria. Africa's average values are higher than the other continents analysed. The three American countries analysed have average emissions of kg CO₂-eq/100 kg milk between 119 and 140. The highest average value is recorded in the USA. Also, the emissions related exclusively to the transport of dairy products were considered. The export routes of goods are synonymous with traffic and transport, which can be by road, rail and sea. Air transport has been ignored.

5.3 The social conditions

Compared with the work done in D3.4, additional synthesis work has been performed here to make the analysis of essential working conditions "immediate" by highlighting the leading indicator for each of the identified categories. In this way a cross-sectional analysis is attempted. The table below lists all the countries involved in the two case studies.

As a **general information**, for all countries assessed, legislative materials were consulted. In almost all cases it was possible to consult national collective agreements directly, and additions were made to the Labor Code or other national laws when the collective agreement referred to this document. In some cases, as in Germany, there are many texts and laws that are referred to and there is no single labour-related text.

It is noticeable throughout the reading that there is a very different degree of complexity and detail in the description of the various existing protections, rights and distinctions of responsibility between employee and employer, across countries. In some cases, approaches that are still immature and partial (or absent) description are recognized.

With regard to the **analysis of working time**, it was considered essential to compare the number of working hours per week. This indicator varies from a minimum of 35 (France), to a maximum of 52 (Zimbabwe). EU (France, Italy and Germany) show the lowest values: 35, 39 and 40 hours per week respectively. This last value is also found in USA, South Africa, Brazil and Argentina. The highest working time is registered in Namibia (45 hour per week), Algeria (44-48 hours per week), Morocco (46 hours per week) and Zimbabwe (52 hours per week). So, with the exception of South Africa which is aligned to Europe and USA, African countries shows the highest working time and Latin America can reach similar values.

In addition, the table also specify the number of allowable overtime hours. The national agreements that have been consulted do not always specify this indicator, as in the case of Algeria, Morocco, Zimbabwe, USA and France. In the countries that specify it, the value is generally similar (2-3 hours per day).

In some countries the overtime is expressed also in hours per week, setting an additional limit: this is the case for example of Namibia, South Africa and

Argentina that pose 3 h/day but no more than 10 h/week, 2 h/day but no more than 12 h/week, 3 h/day but no more than 30 h/month.

Another important theme is the employer's attention to the **continuing education of employees**: in USA and in three African countries this issue is not addressed in contracts, while in the other countries specific leave are envisaged, even if the extent and the level of definition of this right is variable considering different countries. As an extreme example of definition, in France it is based on an individual account of credits for professional development that lasts all the professional life of each worker (*Compte Personnel de Formation*) and the number of hours that can be accumulated are specified by law (up to 150 hours per year, for a maximum of 500 hours). On the other hand, some countries simply state this right in national contracts without giving more details and leaving it to the agreement between employer-employee (Algeria, Morocco).

An informative parameter is related to the **paid leaves** (maternity and paternity leaves). All the countries specify them in the national agreement; the only exceptions are Namibia and Germany where father leave is not explicitly indicated. Mother leave ranges from a minimum of 60 days in Namibia and USA to a maximum of 180 days in Brazil. Moreover, Namibia and USA set a minimum number of months that the worker must have continuously worked in order to have the access to this right: this threshold is 6 and 12 months respectively. Moreover, as for the US, it must be added that the national agreement envisages a sort of "all-inclusive" paid leave: the abovementioned 60 days must cover maternity/paternity leave as well as other leaves needed to take care of relatives (parents, children) with serious health conditions. In some countries the maternity (paid) leave can be extended with a variable non-paid period (e.g. Argentina and Brazil). In France some detailed situations are envisaged, in relation to the number of children and for multiple born.

Father leave, when specified, ranges from 2 days of Algeria and Argentina to 11 days of France, which also envisage extended father leave for multiple born and in case of hospitalization. Morocco and Brazil set their father leave at 3 and 5 days respectively. South Africa and Italy have a father leave with a similar extend to France (10 days). In Zimbabwe, men can profit of a leave of 12 days, but it covers several different reasons, not only father leave. Again,

in the US workers have a paid leave of 60 days, covering different needs (father leave as well as the necessity of taking care of relatives and children).

Brazil makes explicit mention of adoption leave, setting it at 5 days.

In relation to the issue **health and safety**, national agreements have different levels of detail, allowing to half-see different approaches, probably linked to diverse local situations and social context. In some African countries (Algeria, Morocco, South Africa), national laws stress that employees must inform the employer as soon as possible about their absence, in some case (Algeria, Morocco) without giving other details about the right of the workers to be absent for their illness. Also, Argentina and Brazil national agreements mention this right but do not define details about it. Namibia, USA, Germany and Italy set a specific number of days of maximum absence for illness: 30, 60 days, 12 weeks, 180 days respectively. Italy envisages additional not-paid days (up to 6 months) in case of oncology, with the guarantee of the employment for a maximum of 12 months. Germany defines that, in case of illness, the employment is guaranteed for a maximum of 12 weeks. As for US, to have the abovementioned right, employee must have worked continuously at least 12 months.

In relation to **social welfare**, African countries do not give details in their national agreements. All the other countries, with specificities that can also be relevant, envisage different levels of insurance or health care plan, in general financed by the employer, by deduction of salary and, in some case, by the state.

As for **payments**, in the table the minimum pay is displayed. All the values have been transformed from the local currency to euro (€) in order to allow quick comparisons. This value goes from 0.07 €/hour in Namibia to 20.70 €/hour in France, where the minimum pay is set according to the level of specialization of the worker. In all the African and South American countries, the minimum pay is less than 2 €/hour (red lines in the table below), while in the rest of the considered countries (USA and Europe), the minimum is always above 5 €/hour (green lines in the table below), showing a clear geographical gap.

But to be able to make a more precise geographical comparison, purchasing power should be taken into account: in the table below, data related to the cost of living, expressed as cost of living index ([NUMBEO](#)) in all the considered

countries can be found (right column). For the calculation of the index, the term of comparison is the cost of living in New York City (corresponding to 100%): the cost of living in other Countries is expressed as a percentage of the cost of living in NYC.

Crossing the minimum pay and the cost-of-living index table, it is clear that even if in the African and South American countries the cost-of-living index is lower (from 27.94% in Argentina to 36.91% in Zimbabwe), the order of magnitude of minimum pay is “out of scale”. In fact, the cost-of-living index in Africa and South America is roughly a half of the index in USA and Europe, while the minimum pay in Africa and South America is lower.

TABLE 3 COST OF LIVING INDEX

COUNTRY	MINIMUM PAY (€/H)	COST OF LIVING INDEX (%)
<i>New York City</i>		<u>100.00</u>
USA	6.47	75.67
France	10.15-20.70	66.72
Germany	12.00	63.17
Italy	5.60-8.24	59.38
Zimbabwe	0.87	36.91
Brazil	1.47	35.43
South Africa	1.16	33.91
Namibia	0.07	30.85
Morocco	1.05	30.20
Algeria	0.80	29.56
Argentina	0.19	27.94

Source: <https://www.numbeo.com/common/>

In relation to **trade right**, firing has been taken into account. The notice has different dimension in different countries and it goes from 7 days (Namibia and South Africa) to 180 days (Germany) and it often depends on the length of employment. Algeria and Morocco do not specify it in the national agreement. In general, Africa shows shorter notice than America and Europe.

On the subject of **child work**, the minimum age to be eligible for work has been taken into account. This value goes from 14 years (Namibia and Argentina) to 19 years (Algeria), but in many countries there are exceptions and the minimum age can be lower with limitation for dangerous/hard works, or in case of “parent consent” or in case of “family work”. As an example, in

Argentina children can work with their family also under 14 years and in the U.S., children can work with their family from 12-13 years.

TABLE 4 – WORKING CONDITIONS

SDG 8.8.2

COUNTRY	GRI 407-1	GRI 401-2		GRI 403 - 5 GRI 404 - 1, 2, 3	GRI 401 - 2, 3 GRI 404 - 1	GRI 202 – 2 GRI 403– 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10	GRI 201-1 GRI 403- 6	GRI 201-1	GRI 402-1	GRI 408- 1 GRI 409- 1
	GENERAL INFORMATION	WORKING TIME		EDUCATION	PAID LEAVES	HEALTH AND SAFETY	SOCIAL WELFARE	PAYMENTS	TRADE RIGHT	CHILD WORK
	NATIONAL AGREEMENT	WORKING TIME PER WEEK	OVERTIME	PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT	MATERNITY LEAVE & PATERNITY LEAVE	ILLNESS AND WORKPLACE INJURY ALSO WORK-RELATED ILL HEALTH	SOCIAL SERVICES AND INSURANCE	MINIMUM PAY	FIRING	CHILD LABOUR
ALGERIA	Collective agreement + Loi n° 90-11 du 21 Avril 1990 (modifiée et complétée)	44 h	Not specified	Leave is provided to enable the employee to attend professional courses authorised by the employer and to take academic or professional examinations.	Mother: 98 d Father: 2 d	Sick leave: employees must present relevant documents as proof of their illness.	Not specified	0.80 /h 20,000 DZD/monthly	Not specified	Min 19 years Exception: 16-19 years: with parents' consent; night shift forbidden
MOROCCO	Collective agreement + Code du travail	46 h	Not specified	Workers can attend continuing education courses	Mother: 70 d Father: 3 d	Illness or accident must be notified and justified to the employer within 48 h.	Not specified	1.05 €/h 2.094 MAD/month	Not specified	Min 18 years Exception: 15-18 only with permission of the labour inspector
NAMIBIA	Collective agreement + Labour Act	45 h	3 h/d 10 h/week	Not specified	Mother: 60 d (After at least 6 months of continuous employment) Father: Not specified	30-36 d (According to the no. of working days per week).	Not specified	0.07 €/h 5.40 N\$/h	7-30 d notice to employee, depends on the employment length	Min 14 years Note: 14-16 years cannot perform night work (8 pm - 7 am)
SOUTH AFRICA	Collective agreement + "Basic Conditions of Employment Act, nr 75 of 1997 and the Sectoral Determination 13: Farm Worker Sector "	40 h	2 h/d 12 h/week	Not specified	Mother: 4 consecutive months Father: 10 d	10 d/year The employees must notify as soon as possible in case of absence for illness	Not specified	1.16 €/h 23.19 RAND/h	7-30 d notice to employee, depends on the employment length	Min 15 years
ZIMBABWE	Collective agreement + Labour Act (28:01)	52 h	Not specified	Not specified	Mother: 98 d Father: 12 d (Special leave of covering several reasons)	Not specified	Not specified	0.87 €/h 71.926 ZW\$/month	3 months of notice	Min 16 years
ARGENTINA	Collective agreement + Ley de Contrato de Trabajo	40 h	3 h/d 30 h/month 200 h/ year	2 d (consecutive) for educational examinations, max 10 d/year	Mother: 90 d -can be extended 3-6 months without pay Father: 2 d	The employment is guaranteed for the duration of the sick leave.	Workers benefit of a health care plan financed by contributions through deductions of salary, both by worker and employer. Death, illness and disability are covered by a specific and compulsory insurance.	0.19 €/h 16.875 AR\$/month 95,88 AR\$/h	15-60 d notice to the employee Notice not needed if the employer pays an indemnity (15 d' salary, plus 1- or 2- months' salary)	Min 14 years Exception: <14 years: children can work with their family, but they can't perform dangerous tasks; 14-18 years: children can work autonomously with parents' consent
BRAZIL	"Carteira de Trabalho e Previdência Social - CTPS + Consolidação das Leis do Trabalho	40 h	2 h/d	Paid by Workers' Support Fund (FAT) for professional and technological training	Mother: 120-180 d -can be extended to 6 Father: 5 d Adoption: 5 d	Temporary illness does not require a minimum contribution Sickness or disability compensation after at least 12 months of employment	The Brazilian Federation of Workers' Unions (Central Unica dos Trabalhadores) supports workers to obtain guaranteed medical care. However, most of the workers don't have an employment contract, so they cannot profit	1.47 €/h 1.320 R\$/month 246.44 €/month	30 d notice to the employee <u>Without a valid reason:</u> penalty.	Min 16 years Exception: 14-16 years: apprenticeship

							of the association's support and guaranteed medical care.			
U.S.A.	<i>Fair Labour Standards Act (FLSA) Wage and Hour Division (WHD)</i>	40 h	<i>Not specified</i>	<i>Not specified</i>	Both parents: 60 d (After at least 12 months of continuous employment) to take care of parents, spouse, minor/dependent child who has a serious health condition.	60 d for serious illness (After at least 12 months of continuous employment)	Eligible employees and their families are covered by medical, dental and vision insurance. Eligible employees are provided with basic term life insurance and may purchase supplemental insurance. Eligible employees receive basic Long-Term Disability (LTD) coverage.	6.47 €/h 7.25 \$/h	The <u>At Will</u> contract: employer has the right to fire employees at any time; <u>Just Cause</u> : notice needed	Min 16 years <u>Exception</u> : -12-13 years: children can work with a parent -from 14 years: with training certificate or in apprenticeship, children can perform some hazardous occupations
FRANCE	<i>Collective agreement + "Convention Collective nationale proction agricole/CUMA du 15 Septembre 2020"</i>	35 h	<i>Not specified</i>	Workers have an individual account of credits for continuing education, lasting all their working life (Compte Personnel de Formation). Workers accumulate 500 h of training in the CPF, with max 150 h per year	Mother: 80-130 d According to the no. of children <u>Multiple born</u> : 170-230 d Father: 11 d <u>Multiple born</u> : 18 d +30 d in case of hospitalisation	<i>Not specified</i>	Benefits are financed by compulsory contributions paid by employers, employees, as well as by deductions from the state budget. The social service helps you manage the impact of personal or professional difficulties related to your state of health.	10.15-20.70 €/h *according to the level of specialization	30-60 d notice to employee, depends on the employment length	Min 18 years <u>Exception</u> : 16 years: with parents' consent
GERMANY	Absence of a separate labour law code. Labour law is governed by several laws: <i>das Arbeitszeitgesetz (ArbZG); das Bundesurlaubsgesetz (BUrlG); das Entgeltfortzahlungsgesetz (EntgFG); das Teilzeit- und Befristungsgesetz (TzBfG); Das Bürgerliche Gesetzbuch (BGB), that regulates the notice period.</i> <i>Note: Collective agreements between employer/works council are not available for consultation and are not national contracts.</i>	40 h	8 h/week	Workers can take educational leave to attend trainings (e.g., citizenship education, language courses and vocational training)	Mother: 100 d Father: <i>Not specified</i>	Employment guaranteed for 6 weeks, renewable for other 6 weeks.	Workers benefit of a social security plan financed by contributions through deductions of salary, both by worker and employer. Death, unemployment, illness, accidents at work, occupational diseases and disability are covered by a specific and compulsory insurance.	min 12 €/h	15-180 d notice to employee, depends on the employment length	Min 17 years
ITALY	<i>Collective agreement + "Contratto collettivo nazionale di lavoro per gli operai agricoli e florovivaisti"</i>	39 h	5 h/d 18 h/week	200 paid h/3 years 150 h/3 years (remedial courses)	Mother: 100 d Father: 10 d	the employment is guaranteed: 180 d Oncological pathology: + 6 months (not paid) Workplace injury: employment is guaranteed until complete recovery, (max 12 month)	Workers benefit of a social security plan, which also covers accidents, illness, invalidity and involuntary unemployment	5.60-8.24 €/h *According to the level of specialization (monthly)	60 d notice to employee	Min 16 years

6. CLD methodology

In order to create links between factors that are very distant, but related to traded agricultural products and commodities, causal loop diagrams (CLDs) were made. Thanks to this methodology ([MATS, D2.4](#)), it is possible to visualise how the different components of a system actually interact with each other and how changes in one of them can influence other elements. Through the CLDs, it is possible to identify causes-effects within the system, understand the feedback dynamics that can lead to specific behaviours or outcomes, identify leverage points to positively influence the system and predict the effects of changes or interventions on different elements (Probst & Bassi, 2014 - Sterman, 2000).

6.1 The CLD methodology applied to case studies

Focusing on social and environmental sustainability in relation to international trade of beef (#CS 10) and dairy (#CD 13) is undoubtedly challenging. The complexity of these topics lies on the high number of components, on the multiplicity and interdependence of mechanisms and on the diverse effect (positive or negative) that a same action or factor can have on different components of the issue.

Drawing together an overall view is therefore interesting and demanding at the same time.

Specifically, the issue analysed is the sustainability of beef and dairy production and the potential role of current and upcoming policies to increase this sustainability, both on the production and consumption side. The methodology that has been used for the creation of the causal loop diagram is called Systems Thinking⁹. A CLD is a graphical representation of variables and their interconnections, giving shape to the dynamics of a given system.

⁹ Systems Thinking (ST) is an approach that permits to better understand and forecast the outcomes of decisions, across sectors, economic actors, over time and in space (Probst & Bassi, 2014)

The CLD are given in the following two paragraphs and will then be contextualised within the CS. They were created as a team effort, founded on co-creation (with a step by step, participatory approach).

Several factors determine the potential to grow, they can range from profitability, natural resources availability, low salaries, good environmental conditions for ruminant production, in synthesis a good level of competitiveness. On the contrary the same elements can represent a constraint for the beef and dairy production sectors. These are underlying the presence of reinforcing feedback loops or dynamics that stimulate change (e.g., an increase in cost competitiveness results in the growth of farms and in the creation of economies of scale, which further increase cost competitiveness), and balancing feedback loops in the system, or dynamics that counter (oppose) change (e.g., constraints on land availability may result in higher costs, a factor that reduced costs competitiveness and curbs the growth potential of farms), as described as follows.

6.2 CLD in CS #10

At the beginning of the causal loop diagram creation process, we have analysed the key dynamics that determine the farm size, which then affects the cost of production. The farm size has been historically impacted by access to capital, which then allows to reduce the cost of production and increase cost competitiveness, resulting in the further growth of farm size (R1). A growing farm size also influences labour intensity (declining) and the number of animals (increasing). Access to capital also influences technology adoption, which affects labour intensity (reducing it). As a result, employment is impacted both by labour intensity (affected by farm size and technology adoption) and by the number of animals. With higher employment come higher labour costs (both due to the total number of employees and the skill level of employees), showing that labour costs are pushed higher by increased skills (R3), but also pushed lower by reduced labour intensity (B1). We have then explored the implications of the growth of farm size that has occurred historically.

On the one hand, it generates a lock-in effect (with farms becoming bigger and bigger, underlying the dominance of reinforcing loops, via an improvement of cost competitiveness, R2), on the other hand it leads to higher production, economic activity and revenues. This, together with the reduced cost achieved via economies of scale and technology adoption, results in higher

profitability, and hence higher access to capital (as a combination of R1, R2 and R3).

This being considered, constraints also emerged. The higher is production, the lower is beef price (if supply is larger than demand). This would generate a balancing dynamic, that would reduce profitability and the expansion of farms (unless export potential allows to further increase production without affecting local dynamics), but possibly trigger an increase in demand for beef (B5). Further, on the environmental side, higher production results in:

- higher land requirements, feed production, which may face higher costs if land availability is constrained (B3);
- higher manure generation, causing an increase in nutrient concentration per hectare;
- higher GHG emissions.

National and international legislation may limit production when excessive amounts nutrients and emissions are produced (e.g., measured in terms of emissions productivity per ton of meat produced). In the same way, consumer preferences have, in certain instances, shifted to low emission, animal welfare certified products. These emerging dynamics would reduce demand (if sustainability is not addressed, B4) or increase demand, including for export (if sustainability concerns are addressed, R5).

Several intervention options were identified that could support investments in sustainability for beef production. Within sector operations, the adoption of technology (via access to capital) would increase productivity, reducing nutrient concentration and GHG emissions. Lobby groups, animal welfare legislation, and consumer attention could trigger efforts towards labelling of the sustainability of beef, stimulating affecting exports, and beef demand overall. This intervention would generate positive returns for investments in improved sustainability, a factor that is currently -for the most part- an intangible benefit. Concluding, it was assessed that, product sustainability through both improved production practices, animal welfare, land use (e.g., avoided deforestation) and GHG emission reduction can positively impact beef prices (with a premium being applied to sustainable products) and boost export to premium markets. National legislations, lobby groups and consumer attention can support the internalization of intangible benefits, e.g., via product labelling, payments for ecosystem services, generating a stream of revenues that it is in line with sustainability goals.

At the same time, higher profitability and investments in technology can also improve wages, generating a mutually reinforcing synergy between economic, social and environmental performance.

FIGURE 3 CAUSAL LOOP DIAGRAM #CS-10

SOURCE: CRPA AND KE ELABORATION

Depending on the context, it is possible to identify key areas that are specific to a particular country or region.

FIGURE 4 CLS KEYS AREA

SOURCE: CRPA AND KE ELABORATION

Once the CLD is created and the connections between the different factors of interest are highlighted, it is possible to identify the categories that are involved in this case study: land requirement, environmental impact, productivity, production, carbon footprint, labour conditions, market dynamics, profitability and labour supply and skills.

FIGURE 5 CASE STUDY RELATED SDGs

SOURCE: CRPA AND KE ELABORATION

The narrative process that emerges from the writing of the CLD follows the storyline of the case study. This highlights the importance of the factors examined during the research and which represent important connection points between the case study and the storytelling of the dynamics of the milk trade. In particular, it is possible to observe an overlap between the macro-areas highlighted with the blue ovals and the SDGs.

6.3 CLD in CS #13

The issue analysed is the sustainability of dairy production and the potential role of current and upcoming policies to increase sustainability.

At the beginning of the CLD creation process, we have analysed the dynamics that determine the total cost of production of dairy products. At first, we focused on the labour costs, in relation to salaries, as a key cost item. We identified that salaries are impacted by the profitability of operations, which are in turn impacted by revenues (driven by production and market price) and by the total cost of production (including considerations on the total number of cows, employment and labour costs). Considerations were made on the market price, being impacts both by demand and supply. At this stage two feedback loops were identified, one a key determinant of growth (R) related to production resulting in higher profitability and in the expansion of operations, and one being of a balancing nature (B), tending towards equilibrium in relation to the level of salaries provided.

After these initial considerations, the attention moved towards the key drivers of productivity, also a factor affecting the total cost of production. In this context we identified feed quality, genetic improvements, mechanization and robotization as options to increase productivity and reduce the levelized cost of production. On the other hand, national legislation, e.g., on animal welfare, safety and security, while increasing productivity, may also result in higher costs.

As a subsequent step in the creation of the diagram, environmental considerations were added. It was discussed that a higher number of cows would result in increased manure creation, resulting in a higher concentration of nutrients per hectare (e.g., nitrogen and phosphorous). This is a potential limiting factor for the expansion of the animal stock and is represented by a balancing loop (B) in the diagram. On the other hand, if it is possible to expand the land area available for cows, then this constraint is removed, and reinforcing mechanism is introduced (R). This highlight that land availability, depending on specific local contexts, can be an enabling factor but also a constraint to the expansion of the operations in the dairy sector. On the other hand, environmental constraints do remain, especially when considering GHG emissions. When land is available for expansion, and this is realized via deforestation, carbon sequestration would be lost, increasing the GHG

footprint of dairy production. When considering that cows also generate emissions, e.g., via enteric fermentation, GHG intensity may increase.

Several intervention options were identified to remove bottlenecks while increasing the sustainability of dairy production. On the environmental side, reforestation, land restoration and the introduction of renewable energy for farm operations were considered to reduce GHG emissions. Efforts to improve labour and animal conditions were considered to increase revenues (e.g., via subsidies) while at the same time increase productivity. Finally, considerations were made on trade dynamics, with the price of milk import affecting the potential for local production, reason why both improved productivity and environmental sustainability are essential.

Depending on the context, it is possible to identify key parameters that are specific to a particular country or region. For instance, in the African context, the causal loop diagram has highlighted six important factors.

- animal welfare, animal health
- food safety and food security
- total land expansion requirements
- price of imported milk affecting demand for local production
- export/import of milk
- trade union agreements
- public subsidies

Animal health and welfare have become key factors in trading internationally, especially with countries belonging to the European Union.

FIGURE 6 CAUSAL LOOP DIAGRAM - DAIRY SECTOR

Source: CRPA and KE elaboration

FIGURE 7 CLS KEYS AREA

Source: CRPA and KE elaboration

Once the CLD is created and the connections between the different factors of interest are highlighted, it is possible to identify the categories that are involved in this case study: land requirement, environmental impact, productivity, production, carbon footprint, labour conditions, market dynamics, profitability and labour supply and skills.

FIGURE 8 CASE STUDY RELATED SDGs

Source: CRPA and KE elaboration

The narrative process that emerges from the writing of the CLD follows the storyline of the case study. This highlights the importance of the factors examined during the research and which represent important connection points between the case study and the storytelling of the dynamics of the milk trade. In particular, it is possible to observe an overlap between the macro-areas highlighted with the blue ovals and the SDGs.

7. Key conclusions and linkages

The representation of the beef and dairy supply chain through casual loop diagram shows the complexity of this sector and how social, environmental and economic sustainability are strongly connected. For example, the CLD created for CS #10 suggest that aligning with sustainability goals, national regulations, consumer awareness, and labelling initiatives can internalize intangible benefits, creating revenue streams for what concerns beef production in selected countries. For what concerns CS #13, its CLD suggested that improving labor and animal conditions can boost revenues and productivity, possibly through subsidies. Trade dynamics, especially the impact of milk imports on local production, underscore the importance of both productivity improvement and environmental sustainability.

It is evident that in a food trading system there will be “*balancing*” loops and “*reinforcing*” loops at the same time. In case of *balancing loops*, when a specific element increases, another connected element decreases. In case of *reinforcing loops*, when a specific element increases, another linked element will increase simultaneously.

7.1 Identification of scenarios

This complexity can be summarized in different scenarios:

Scenario 1 - *When there is a significant difference in terms of production costs at farm level between two countries, the less competitive country can import beef commodities from the more competitive one, probably at a lower price than the local production.*

The import of beef and dairy commodities can help the less competitive country to nourish its population at reasonable price (*SDG2 - Zero hunger*). At the same time, this import can impact the local production, which is not competitive in terms of costs/prices, with the product offered by the world market. Low prices of imported commodities will discourage local production, limiting the number of farms and cattle, limiting revenues and profitability, leading to a reduction of employment in the beef and dairy primary production and impacting consequently on the social dimension (*SDG8 - Decent work and economic growth* and *SDG3- Good health and wellbeing*). Local producer will be also under pressure to become more competitive increasing their productivity. Furthermore, a reduction in production would lead to a reduction

in the number of cattle and consequently less land will be required to produce feed for livestock or for pasture (*SDG15 - Life on Land*). This would create an impact on the environmental dimension, with a decrease in manure production per hectare and a reduction in local CO₂ emission (*SDG13 - Climate action*). On the other side, the import of beef commodities will generate CO₂ emissions related to transport.

In this case the balancing loop is quite clear: the need to improve *SDG2 - Zero hunger* by importing dairy and beef products has a negative impact on *SDG8 - Decent work and economic growth* and *SDG3- Good health and wellbeing* and a possible positive impact on *SDG15 - Life on Land* and *SDG13 - Climate action*.

Scenario 2 - *When there is a significant difference in terms of production costs at farm level between two countries, the most competitive country can export beef commodities to the less competitive one.*

This export would support the local production of the more competitive country. Market prices will guarantee revenues and profitability leading to a stable/increasing production with consequent increasing employment in cattle farms, impacting the social dimension (*SDG8 - Decent work and economic growth* and *SDG3 Good health and wellbeing*). Good revenues and profits can also lead to an increasing investment in technologies, bringing to better working conditions, and to an increasing need of skilled workers. This could lead to operate for workers education and training. At the same time, a stable/increasing production would require a higher number of cows, possible with higher productivity, and consequently more land is required to produce feed for livestock or for pasture (*SDG15 - Life on Land*). This would create an impact on the environmental dimension, with an increase in manure production and nutrient concentration per hectare and in local CO₂ emission (*SDG13 - Climate action*). In addition, export will generate CO₂ emissions related to transport.

In this case the balancing loop is quite clear, the possibility to export commodities on the world market has a positive impact on *SDG8 - Decent work and economic growth* and *SDG3- Good health and wellbeing*, while there will be a possible negative impact on *SDG15 - Life on Land* and *SDG13 - Climate action*.

Scenario 3 - *When the difference in beef or dairy production costs between two countries is very small and the price in the world market for commodities is very close, the import and export between two countries is due to the need of a specific product to meet an internal demand.*

In this case the casual loop diagram arrows can have double directions. In both countries beef or dairy export will support local production and at the same time imported beef/dairy commodities help to nourish local populations at reasonable price (*SDG2 - Zero hunger*). Market prices will guarantee revenues able to meet production costs level; profitability will be low, leading to a stable or increasing production but, simultaneously, bringing to a decreasing number of farms and cows due to the increasing productivity. Productivity pressure will generate investments, reducing the employment in the farms but hiring skilled workers, with higher salary and better working conditions, impacting the social dimension (*SDG8 - Decent work and economic growth and SDG3 - Good health and wellbeing*). The increasing productivity will reduce, in relative terms, the need for land to produce feed for livestock or for pasture (*SDG15 - Life on Land*). This would create an impact on the environmental dimension by reducing, in relative terms, manure production and nutrient concentration per hectare, but increasing the total local CO₂ emission (*SDG13 - Climate action*). In parallel, the import and export will generate CO₂ emissions related to transport.

In all different scenarios the situation is more complex than described, in fact the positive and negative impacts on SGDs can be mitigated by external factors and national policies such as:

- consumers or society needs/requirements (such as animal welfare, environmental requirements, change in diets);
- labour Unions can affect labour conditions and labour costs;
- energy costs can affect production and transport;
- public subsidies can affect production at different levels.

Besides that, *Trade Agreements* can play a significant role in products exchange. Specific trade tools can be implemented to limit or promote trade activities: tariffs, quotas, voluntary export restraints, export taxes, export subsidies.

7.2 Scenario development within CS #13

The data collected and organised by CRPA were transformed into CLDs through joint work with KE, which also took care of translating these values into a mathematical model. By doing so, it is possible to observe and evaluate how values change as certain variables increase/decrease.

This kind of methodology has been applied in case study no. 13 to three different countries: Algeria, Germany and the U.S.

The scenario examined is the Business as Usual (BAU), which assumes no changes to the current practices. This scenario assumes that each country continues its current trajectory without any significant alterations to production, trade, or social conditions related to the dairy industry. In other words, each country produces according to its current practices, and trade dynamics remain unchanged (MATS D3.3).

In the alternative scenario there are specific changes in production and trade patterns designed to achieve a better trade balance and align production with domestic demand. The implications are different for different countries. In the case of Algeria, production is adjusted to be sufficient to meet domestic demand (higher productivity and larger number of cows per farm). This implies that Algeria is working towards self-sufficiency in dairy production, aiming to produce enough to satisfy its own consumption needs. Further, this scenario also includes an aim to improve social conditions in Algeria (via higher salaries). Concerning Germany and the U.S., in contrast to the BAU case, where production remains unchanged, the alternative scenario involves a reduction in production. This reduction is aligned with national demand in these countries, suggesting a more intentional approach to avoid overproduction and align production with local consumption patterns (MATS D3.3).

The alternative scenario implies changes in the trade dynamics between countries. With Algeria producing more to meet its domestic demand, and with improved social conditions, there will be a decreased reliance on imports. The Government of Algeria has, in fact, reopened the imports of dairy cattle in 2022 to reduce the imports of milk powder and improve local milk production (USDA, 2022). Nevertheless, the implications of this policy have not been clearly identified, calling for a modelling approach that can allow

understanding the socio-economic implications that would arise from a decrease in imports of dairy products (MATS D3.3).

Meanwhile, Germany and the USA, with reduced production, will experience changes in their export capacities.

The main assumptions used in the alternative scenario, are as follows:

- Algeria:
 - an increase in milk productivity from 3,550 kg/cow per year to 4,850 kg/cow per year (+36%)
 - an increase in the average farm size from 18 to 50 cows (2.7x increase)
 - an increase of the salary level from USD 2,430 per person per year to USD 16,000 (6.6x increase)
- Germany:
 - a reduction in the average farm size from 313 to 244 cows, or reduction of farms in the range of 20%.
- USA:
 - a reduction in the average farm size from 500 to 450 cows, or reduction of farms in the range of 10%.

Results show that Algeria would produce at higher unit cost (1.01 USD/kg, as opposed to 0.81 USD/kg in the BAU scenario), while at the same time improving profitability (-0.1 USD/kg, as opposed to -0.29 USD/kg in the BAU scenario). The cost increase is primarily the result of higher labor costs, while the reduction is primarily due to higher productivity per cow. Overall, annual milk production per farm could increase to 243,000 kg in the alternative scenario, as opposed to 64,000 kg in the BAU case. Total annual milk production at the country level would increase to 6.7 billion kg in the alternative scenario, against 1.77 billion kg in the BAU (MATS D3.3).

In the case of Germany, production per farm would decline to 2.4 million kg/year, compared to 3.08 million kg/year in the BAU. At the national level the reduction reaches 8.3 billion kg/year. Reduced production results in lower CO₂ emissions, in the range of 0.9 million kg/year (MATS D3.3).

Similarly, for the USA, production per farm would decline to 5.09 million kg/year, compared to 5.65 million kg/year in the BAU. At the national level

the reduction reaches 10.8 billion kg/year. Reduced production results in lower CO₂ emissions, in the range of 0.95 million kg/year (MATS D3.3).

To summarize for a policy-makers perspective, the selected scenarios for these countries aimed at achieving self-sufficiency, reflecting a shift in production dynamics. In other words, it means that Algeria increased its beef and dairy production, while Germany and the U.S. saw a decrease. In an effort to promote social sustainability, we implemented measures like salary increases in Algeria, contributing to the well-being of the workforce.

These scenarios not only predict changes in how these countries trade with each other but also emphasize the potential for greater profitability in specific sectors within Algeria. Additionally, there is room for a significant reduction in carbon emissions in both Germany and the U.S. These insights underscore the intricate relationship between economic, social, and environmental sustainability.

To sum it up, the results suggest that considering competitiveness as a key criterion for economic sustainability leads to significant trade-offs among economic, social, and environmental implications. This becomes particularly evident when we take into account the diverse governance and social conditions, such as labor laws and working conditions, that exist at the national level.

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